

D6.2 Report on the One Health EJP Communication and Media workshop (Y3)

WP6: Education and Training

Responsible Partner: UoS (P23)

GENERAL INFORMATION

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Introduction

The CaM Workshop’s main aim was to aid early career researchers and develop their communication skills to disseminate information effectively to the general public and to their key stakeholders. By covering all media distribution formats (television, radio, the Internet, social media, direct public events, etc.), our goal was to equip the participants with the knowledge on how to generate the maximum impact of their research towards their target audiences.

The main organisers of the CaM workshop were the NDRVMI, Risk Assessment Center on Food Chain (RACFC) and Surrey University, UK. The original plan was to organise a physical event hosted in Sofia, Bulgaria on the 5th and 6th October 2020. Approximately 50 guests (delegates, organisers and lecturers) were planned to be accommodated in a hotel, which also had a conference room to host the

workshop. Due to travel restrictions and the measures put in place in response to the COVID-19 pandemic, the physical event was re-organised as a virtual one.

This did not pose a big challenge, as it took away some of the complications which are brought by physically hosted events. Furthermore, this made the workshop easier to attend by guests from distant countries, since it eliminated the long travel time and costs.

We considered two platforms for the virtual event - Google Meet and Zoom. We proceeded with using Zoom's video-conferencing software, since it offered break out rooms and easier file sharing functionalities, both of which were key for the interactive part of the event. Google Meet's main limitation was that files could not be shared with those who did not have Google Mail accounts.

Thanks to the lockdown measures brought by COVID, most of the attendees were already accustomed to virtual meetings and events. However, a short visual user manual with screenshots on how to enter the Zoom meeting room, how to use the platform and the general workshop etiquette was provided alongside the meeting link and the password. A contact for technical support was provided in this manual and in all email correspondences.

Moderating meetings in Zoom was effective and very successful ensuring smooth and clear transitions between the sessions. The group break out room sessions were also moderated when required, and the live mock interviews worked very well using the 'spotlight' feature. Overall, the virtual event didn't have any interruptions, delays or other technical issues.

Theme and Overview

The theme of the workshop and media training was "One Health EJP Communication and Media Workshop: How Science Achievements Reach People and Contribute to a Better Life". Its core aim was to ease the dissemination of research achievements by young researchers to the general public, scientists and stakeholders. In addition to that, information which is more easily accessible plays a significant part in enhancing food safety and public health. With the correct and meaningful form of communication through all types of media (television, radio, the Internet, direct public events, etc.) a better and more sustainable relationship can be formed between research institutes and the general public.

Aims and Objectives

The aims and the objectives of the workshop can be summarized in the 3 following points:

1. To equip researchers with the knowledge, practices and skills required for effective communication of science research in food safety, public and veterinary health. Furthermore, the workshop aimed to demonstrate the different ways in which communication must be tailored between different audiences such as the general public, stakeholders, media journalists and private media.
2. To learn about the importance of a communications strategy, the importance of having an online presence (including a personal brand) and how to best utilize different social media platforms such as LinkedIn and Twitter from a scientific perspective in the area of public and veterinary health and food safety.
3. The workshop aimed to provide extensive information on the ways in which specialists from the Risk Assessment Center on Food Chain communicate risks of all kinds to the general public, following EFSA guidelines.

Speakers

The workshop boasted leading communication experts in public health from academia and industry, with a specific focus on food safety and risk assessment, and included training by a former TV News broadcaster, presenter and reporter who is an expert on media performance and media interviews. The OHEJP Communications Team also delivered a session to inform participants of the importance of a communications strategy, an online presence, the importance and use of a social media strategy, the importance of creating a personal brand and events communications.

The biographies and photos of the speakers can all be found on the [Communication and Media Workshop page](#) on the OHEJP website.

Programme Structure

The programme duration was between 6.5 and 7.5 hours each day, with lunch breaks and coffee breaks (see [annex 3](#)). This programme was finalised and made available before the call for applications was launched.

The programme was delivered by the experts on Zoom platform (see logistical arrangements for further details). The pre-reading materials included an instruction manual on how to use the Zoom platform, a short list of example materials for the breakout session rooms and a list of the breakout rooms.

Before the event, the organisers were open to any questions about the event itself. During the event, there was a Q&A slot after each of the sessions and most of the lecturers provided their email addresses for any further discussions, which could not fit in the time frame of their session.

To ensure the workshop was interactive despite being online, delegates participated in group-work presentation exercises, and even had the opportunity to attend and participate in exemplary 'live' public media mock interviews on their topical research area, teaching them how to answer the questions of journalists and how to deliver their key messages effectively to their target audiences.

The comprehensive workshop programme provided delegates with the opportunity to learn from experts about risk communication, EU communication campaigns, and the coordination of communication activities and strategies related to public health and food safety risks.

Delegates also learned techniques and tools to communicate their research more effectively- examples include the creation of a communication strategy, brand awareness, the use of social media, how to deliver successful public media interviews and the role of popular scientific journals.

Logistical arrangements

The time-slot for each speaker provided them with sufficient time to deliver a thorough explanation on their topic. After each block of talks, there was a short break and each day had a 1-hour long lunch break. During two of the longer topics there was an additional 10 minute break.

The Bulgarian lecturers were invited to present their topics in a conference room at RACFC. Their presentations were submitted a week before the event to the organising team and subsequently managed by said team. During the two days of presentation, there was a host and co-host computer. The host computer was the one, from which the Virtual Event Manager was moderating the whole event, whereas the co-host system was used by the lecturers. Additionally, we had a 3rd system which was recording the whole event using Zoom's built-in solution.

Before the event, all the participants received confirmation emails, as well as instruction emails. The instruction emails contained a short visual manual on how to navigate the Zoom platform and how to access the breakout rooms, a breakout rooms list and the example cases, which were going to be helpful in the breakout rooms session. In addition to that, the email contained a direct invitation link, a Meeting ID and password for the meeting, and the time reference of the event making the time zone very clear for the international audience.

Two particular sessions in this programme had an interactive element to them - Roz Morris (TV News London) and Mihail Milanov (NDRVI). Roz's session incorporated live mock interviews with two previously selected candidates – a One Health EJP PhD student, and an OHEJP WP6 alumni member. These candidates were recruited by the WP6 team. Roz and the candidate were put in the “spotlight”, so they were the focus of the presentation during the interview. Mihail's session included breakout rooms during day 2 of the event. The participants were assigned to different rooms based on their locality. The idea was to create diverse groups, which could exchange know-how from different parts of the world. The breakout rooms list was emailed to the participants alongside the reminder note that they received on each of the days of the event. It was also sent in the Zoom chat 10 minutes before the session started in case they lost access to the previously sent files.

The OHEJP Communications team pre-recorded their video and the organisation team played it from the co-host computer according to schedule. Afterwards they lead a live Q&A session.

Promotional Campaign

The promotional campaign was managed by the One Health EJP Communications Team and began at the start of August 2020, with a [‘Save the Date’ promotional flyer](#), which communicated the theme of the workshop, dates, location (online) and target audience. This first flyer was disseminated through the internal OHEJP communication channels (monthly education and training activities bulletin) and external OHEJP communication channels (OHEJP website, social media, One Health Commission social media channels).

A dedicated [web-page](#) was created for the Communication and Media workshop in August 2020 which initially described when, where and how much it costs to attend the workshop, along with the save the date flyer, aims of the event and eligibility rules.

A second [full event flyer](#) was created to provide more detailed information about the concept and theme of the workshop, the aims and objectives and target audience. It also provided a link to the application form created by the communications team to attend the workshop, along with the deadline. This was disseminated through the same internal and external channels described for the save the date flyer.

As the speakers were confirmed for the final programme, they were asked to provide short biographies and a headshot photo. These were added to the website page as they were received leading up to the event, and the announcement of these speakers for the CaM workshop was also shared on social media to increase awareness of the event and

traffic to the OHEJP website. Please note, almost all speaker biographies and photos were published before the full event flyer was published and the application process was opened to encourage the submission of applications.

The communications team created branded visual montages from the screenshots and testimonials captured. These montages were used to report and share the successes of this workshop through a [blog post](#), on the [One Health EJP CaM workshop webpage](#). This was shared through the One Health EJP social media channels- [Twitter](#) and [LinkedIn](#), and the following [monthly education and training activities bulletins](#) and [OHEJP newsletters](#) published in 2020.

Applications and selection procedure

In total, 55 applications were received from 24 countries across the world. The 55 applicants for the Communication and Media workshop were from a range of educational backgrounds (see figure below). This was considered during the selection process to ensure that there was enough diversity of interdisciplinary backgrounds because it would bring many different perspectives and initiate collaborative discussions.

Applicants also had a range of educational levels (see figure below), which was once again an important consideration because the workshop aimed to train Early Career Researchers. It was important to have a range of educational levels to stimulate discussions and collaborations between the delegates but also so that those at undergraduate level could learn from their peers with more experience.

The 55 applications were screened using the selection criteria below by the local organising team, and then checked for gender balance. 40 delegates were selected.

- Consortium members vs. Non- Consortium members
- Experience
- Educational background
- Highest Education Level
- Area of expertise
- Motivation to participate

Since the event was held virtually, most of the applicable candidates were approved and no single criteria could be picked as leading. The diversity of the delegate group was insured by the fact that it included multiple nationalities, age groups and areas of expertise.

Educational Background

53 responses

Highest Education Level

53 responses

Delegates

The organisers and speakers delivered a high-quality course consisting of theoretical and practical elements of communication to 40 delegates from 18 countries.

Delegates were from various career stages, including bachelor's students, master's students, PhD students, early career post-doctoral researchers and doctors of human and veterinary medicine.

The delegates represented all pillars of One Health, including veterinary medicine, human medicine, biological sciences, environmental sciences, pharmaceutical sciences, public health, infectious diseases, microbiology, mathematics, social sciences, economics and communications. Bringing together people from across disciplines made this workshop truly cross- disciplinary and highlighted the advantages of a One Health approach.

The attendance of delegates from diverse backgrounds allowed for interesting collaborative discussions and for knowledge and experiences to be shared.

Testimonials

The testimonials were captured in the feedback evaluation forms collected from delegates. Permission to publish these testimonials was obtained during the registration process. Please see the testimonials from our delegates below.

The testimonials of the two delegates who participated in the live mock interviews can be found highlighted in the the [blog post](#).

Lead Organiser Testimonial

Professor Hristo Daskalov, Bulgarian Food Safety Agency- "During the workshop I realized the universality of the work we do as scientists. Even when we're talking about a niche in science, such as the area of food safety, the amount of research and data that we collect accumulates to something that, if properly communicated to the public, can help solve a lot of diseases and ease suffering. By meeting so many foreign experts, even only via the internet, we were able to exchange great ideas and managed to learn through the experience of others. The communication of scientific research should start between experts and the workshop managed to do exactly that - it helped us start a discussion, which should and will be continued for quite some time."

Examples of Delegate Testimonials collected

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"I loved participating in the mock interviews it was a very nice learning experience."
Laura Gonzalez Villeta, University of Surrey, UK

"I am glad I was a part of the One Health EJP Communication and Media workshop as it has taught me, among other things, the importance of having an online presence to share my results with public and other scientists. All the tips on improving my communication skills I obtained during this workshop I can apply to my presentations immediately. It was all well worth it, thank you!"
Filip Damek, OHEJP ToxSAUQMRA PhD student, ANSES, France

"The Communication and Media Workshop taught me that university name can be used as brand to communicate your research. It was an amazing experience to participate in an exemplary media interview which taught us how to deal with the questions of journalists and pitch our messages effectively."
Tanveer Munir, Ecole Superieur du Bois, France

"I really enjoy the breakout workshop where we have learnt from our experiences and created a presentation that reflects our different contexts."
Gerome Sambou, Ministry of livestock and animal production of Senagal, Senegal

"Thank you very much for facilitating this course! I really learnt a lot about risk communication and successful communication of research results. It gave me a possibility to exchange experience with communication of research results with participants from European and Asian countries representing different cultural and professional backgrounds."
Zuzana Nordeng, Norwegian Institute of Public Health (NIPH), Norway

"Engaging, thought-provoking and comprehensive workshop involving people all across Europe and the world"
Patrick Lennard, Leiden University, the Netherlands

Photos

Written permission was taken from all those in any photographs taken. This was done during the registration application process. The montage below was created by the OHEJP communications team.

Blog post

Work Package 6 worked closely with the One Health EJP Communications Team to create a blog post to promote the successes of the event, publish photos and testimonials. The published blog post can be found on the One Health EJP website [here](#).

This blog post was promoted in the Education and Training activities monthly bulletins, OHEJP newsletters and through the official OHEJP social media channels.

Recording

The workshop was recorded on both days by the local organisers, and a copy of the files have been sent to WP6 for further use.

Internal Events Survey information

Name of the activity:	One Health EJP Communication and Media workshop		
Date:	5 th – 6 th October 2020		
Place:	Online event (Zoom)		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference	No	Participation to a Conference	No
Organisation of a Workshop	Yes	Participation to a Workshop	No
Press release	No	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	No
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)	No	Video/Film	No
Exhibition	No	Brokerage Event	No
Flyer	Yes	Pitch Event	No
Training	Yes	Trade Fair	No
Social Media	Yes	Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	No
Website	Yes	Other	No
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)	No		
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	48	Media	1
Industry	1	Investors	0
Civil Society	0	Customers	0
General Public	0	Other	0
Policy Makers	0		

Annex 1: "Save the Date" Promotional Flyer

Save the Date!
Communications and Media Workshop 2020
How Science Achievements Reach People
and Contribute to a Better Life

Date:

5th and 6th October 2020

Location:

This will now be a free to attend virtual event.

Audience:

PhD Students & Early Career Researchers (<5 years post-PhD)
from relevant background

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#OneHealthEJP #OHEJPCAMworkshop

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Annex 2: CaM workshop full Promotional Flyer

Communications and Media Workshop 2020 How Science Achievements Reach People and Contribute to a Better Life

Date:

5th and 6th October 2020

Location:

This will now be a free to attend virtual event.

Audience:

PhD Students & Early Career Researchers (<5 years post-PhD)
from relevant background

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Aim of the CaM Workshop

Introducing the general public and all stakeholders to the achievements of science and their real meaning for people's lives plays a key role in enhancing food safety and public health.

The connection / communication of the new knowledge received with the wide range of stakeholders and organizations (private and state) are no less important than the process of knowledge acquisition itself. The need for public support and understanding is indisputable, especially on such a sensitive issue as food safety with regard to zoonotic agents, antimicrobial resistance and emerging biological hazards to human health.

The European Union brings together over 500m inhabitants living in 28 different countries with a different mentality, specific features that resolve crises in a different way, including those related to food safety and health. At the same time, the influence of the media in any form (television, radio, the Internet, direct public events, etc.) is indisputable for creating a relationship and gaining confidence from the audience in terms of scientific knowledge.

The question of how to convey accurate information whilst also captures the minds and souls of people is key to any communication. This is the main goal of the organized workshop of scientists from the organizations participating in the scientific project.

This workshop will consist of sessions delivered by leading European experts in this field, practical and interactive workshops and sessions, and will uniquely bring together the participants' practical experience facilitating subsequent discussion which will allow assessment of the risk communication practices and the role of the private and public media (including social media strategies) in this process.

To register for this event: [click here](#)

Registration closes at 12 midnight CEST on 11th September 2020.

Annex 3: CaM workshop Programme

One Health EJP Communications and Media Workshop 2020 How Science Achievements Reach People and Contribute to a Better Life

Date: 5th and 6th October 2020

CEST MONDAY

- 09.00 **WELCOME**
Prof. Yanko Ivanov, Deputy Minister of Ministry of Agriculture, Food and Forestry
- 09.10 **Meet and greet & introduction to agenda.**
Prof. Hristo Daskalov, NDRVI
- 09.20 **Communicating Success**
OHEJP Communications Team, UoS
- 09.50 **Introduction to food chain basic risk management & specific considerations for communication within the risk analysis process.**
Dr Iliyan Kostov, Risk Assessment Center on Food Chain
- 10.20 *Coffee break*
- 10.40 **EU communication campaigns in area of food safety science.**
Prof. Hristo Daskalov, NDRVI
- 11.10 **Practices of the Risk Assessment Center on the Food Chain and Risk Communication Activities with the participation of EFSA and other organizations responsible for risk.**
Prof. Georgi Georgiev, Risk Assessment Center on Food Chain
- 11.40 **Bulgarian Focal point of EFSA and Risk Communication: EFSA best practices and joint efforts for public interest and awareness.**
Dr Donka Popova, Risk Assessment Center on Food Chain, Ministry of Agriculture, Food and Forestry
- 12.10 *Lunch break*
- 13.10 **The role of scientific research and media communications in the process of introducing market innovation that increase food safety and nutrition.**
Mr. Kiril Petkov, CEO and Co-Founder, ProViotic
- 14.40 *Coffee break*
- 15.00 **The role of scientific research and media communications in the process of introducing market innovation that increase food safety and nutrition.**
Mr. Kiril Petkov, CEO and Co-Founder, ProViotic
- 16.00 *Coffee break*
- 16.10 **The role of popular scientific journals in communicating scientific achievements and innovations.**
Dr Milena Krastanova - Editor in Chief of Journal of Veterinary Assembly
- 16.40 *Close of Day One*
Prof. Hristo Daskalov, NDRVI

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One Health EJP Communications and Media Workshop 2020 How Science Achievements Reach People and Contribute to a Better Life

Date: 5th and 6th October 2020

CEST TUESDAY

- 09.30 **Welcome back and Summary of Day 1**
Prof. Hristo Daskalov, NDRVI
- 09.40 **The media and the different social and age groups of the population - how to accept news in science and its credibility.**
Ms Martina Marinova - BFSA
- 10.10 **Scientists and journalists - how can we help each other.**
Prof. Hristo Daskalov, NDRVI
- 10.40 *Coffee break*
- 11.00 **Researchers and public media.**
Roz Morris, TV News London
- 12.30 **Break-out groups (work in groups to show practices (authority website, interview of people in charge, leaflets, information campaigns in the media (newspapers, television, Facebook, direct meetings with stakeholders, etc.) in different countries.**
Dr Mihail Milanov - representative of NDRVI
- 13.10 *Lunch break*
- 14.10 **Groups present views and discussion.**
Dr Mihail Milanov - representative of NDRVI
- 14.50 **Coordination of communication activities related to public health and food safety risks, state-level strategies and participation of business organizations and other interested organizations.**
Dr Evgeny Makaveev - Director of Risk Communication Department
- 15.20 **General discussion of communication on food safety science and public health.**
Prof. Hristo Daskalov, Dr Iliyan Kostov and Prof. Georgi Georgiev
- 15.50 **Future perspective and closing remarks.**
Prof. Hristo Daskalov, NDRVI
- 16.00 *Close of workshop*

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